

Solid-State Photoswitching of Hydrazones Based on Excited-State Intramolecular Proton Transfer

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1. Synthesis and characterization

Experimental

Reactions were monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) carried out on silica plates (Merck silica gel 60 F-254), visualized by irradiation with UV light (256 nm).

Commercially available reagents were used without further purification. Synthesis of starting materials was performed according to literature procedures or as specified.

Basic ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on 600, 300 MHz (Agilent-Varian VNMRS), 400 MHz (Bruker Ascend) for ^1H nuclei and 150, 75 MHz (Agilent -Varian VNMRS), 101 MHz (Bruker Ascend) for ^{13}C nuclei. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were also recorded on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer with a broad-band cryo probe with ATM module (5 mm CPBBO BB-1H/19F/15N/D Z-GRD) operating at 500 MHz for ^1H and 125.7 MHz for ^{13}C . ^{15}N NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer with an inverse triple resonance cryo probe with an ATM module (5 mm CPTCI $^1\text{H}/^{13}\text{C}/^{15}\text{N}/\text{D}$ Z-GRD) operating at 600.1 MHz for ^1H , 150.9 MHz for ^{13}C and 60.8 MHz for ^{15}N . For NMR signal assignment in solution, standard Bruker pulse sequences for 1D (^1H , ^{13}C -APT) and 2D (COSY, ROESY, HSQC, HMBC) NMR experiments at a corrected temperature of 298 K were employed, measuring all samples in DMSO- d_6 . Liquid-state NMR data were interpreted using Topspin 3.5 and references to the solvent signals: DMSO- d_6 : $\delta=2.50$ (1H) and $\delta=39.7$ ppm (^{13}C). Chemical shifts are reported in δ units, parts per million (ppm); signals are referenced to TMS as an internal standard. Coupling constants (J) are given in Hz and multiplicity is abbreviated as: s (singlet), d (doublet), dd (doublet of doublets), t (triplet), qd (quartet of doublets), m (multiplet). Basic NMR experiments were performed at corrected 298.15 K temperature.

The HRMS measurements were performed on the machine with ion source HESI (heated electrospray) with mass analyzer orbitrap (Orbitrap Velos Pro Thermo Scientific). Synthesis of corresponding ketones was performed according to our previously reported work.^{1,2}

1.1. General procedures for hydrazone synthesis

9, **R** = $-\text{NO}_2$
10, **R** = $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$
11, **R** = $-\text{H}$

1, **R** = $-\text{H}$
2, **R** = $-\text{NO}_2$
3, **R** = $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$

Scheme S1 Synthesis of studied pentafluorophenyl triaryl-HZ photoswitches.

Synthetic procedure A: specifically used to obtain both *E* and *Z* isomers for further characterizations.

To a stirred solution of ketone (0.65 mmol) and CF_3COOH (0.1 ml) in CHCl_3 (5 ml) was added pentafluorophenylhydrazine (0.65 mmol) in one portion. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1-16 h. Reaction mixture was cooled down to room temperature and washed by distilled water (2×10 ml). Organic phase was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Crude mixture was separated by flash chromatography.

Synthetic procedure B: specifically used for the preparation of compounds **2** and **3** in powder form enriched with the *Z* isomer, avoiding chromatographic separation.

To a stirred solution of ketone **9** or **10** (0.65 mmol) and CF_3COOH (0.1 ml) in EtOH (4 ml) was added pentafluorophenylhydrazine (0.65 mmol) in one portion. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min till precipitation of the product occurs. After that, the reaction mixture was stirred and refluxed another 8 h. After cooling the reaction mixture to room temperature, the precipitate was separated by filtration and washed by cold EtOH (10 ml). The hydrazones **2** and **3** were isolated as almost pure *Z* isomers (90:10 ratio of *Z*:*E*).

2-((2-(perfluorophenyl)hydrazinylidene)(phenyl)methyl)pyridine (1)

Synthetic procedure A: Hydrazones (*E*)-**1** and (*Z*)-**1** were isolated from crude reaction mixture by flash chromatography (SiO₂, Hexanes:EtOAc (3:1)); **overall yield 193 mg (81 %)**, isomers isolated in ratio 1 : 2.3 (*Z* : *E*).

(*Z*)-**1** (58 mg) pale yellow solid, m.p. = 135-137 °C, ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 13.10 (bs, 1H, H11), 8.82 (d, *J* = 4.3 Hz, 1H, H1), 7.99 (ddd, *J* = 7.8, 7.8 Hz, 1.6 Hz, 1H (H3)), 7.56 (dd, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 5.3 Hz, 1H, H2), 7.50 - 7.47 (m, 2H, H8), 7.46 - 7.41 (m, 3H, H9, H10), 7.35 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H, H4) ppm; ¹³C NMR (151

MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, signals for mixture of isomers *E:Z* (1:7)) δ: 155.9, 152.4, 149.0, 148.9, 148.8, 148.6, 143.2, 138.6, 138.0, 137.0, 131.9, 129.5, 129.5, 129.0, 128.9, 128.8, 125.8, 124.8, 123.6, 120.7 ppm (perfluorinated aromatic ring: 139,0; 137,4; 121,2 ppm); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.2 (C5), 147.6 (C1), 142.5 (C6), 138.2 (C7), 137.1 (C3), 128.9 (C9), 128.5 (C10), 128.4 (C8), 125.4 (C4), 123.4 (C2) ppm (without signals of perfluorinated aromatic ring); ¹⁹F NMR (376MHz, CDCl₃) δ: -156.60 (m 2F, F12), -164.00 (m, 2F, F13) -168.27 (dddd, *J* = 21.78 Hz, 21.78 Hz, 4.87 Hz, 4.87 Hz, 1F, F14) ppm; IR: $\tilde{\nu}_{\max}$ 3061 (w, N-H), 1655 (w), 1578 (w), 1520 (s), 1437 (s), 1212 (m), 1114 (s), 1000 (s), 969 (s), 796 (s), 700 (s), 635 (s), 562 (s) cm⁻¹. HRMS (ESI): *m/z* for C₁₈H₁₁F₅N₃⁺ ([M + H]⁺) found 364,0869; calcd. C₁₈H₁₁F₅N₃⁺ ([M + H]⁺) 364,0868.

(*E*)- **1**, (135 mg) white solid, m.p. = 139 – 141 °C; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 8.40 (ddd, *J* = 4.8 Hz, 1.7 Hz, 0.9 Hz, 1H (H1)), 8.37 (bs, 1H, H11), 7.98 (ddd, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 8.1 Hz 1.0 Hz, 1H, H4), 7.82 (ddd, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 7.8 Hz, 1.8 Hz, 1H, H3), 7.55 (d, *J* = 7,41 Hz, 2H, H9), 7.52 - 7.47 (m, 1H, H10), 7.33 (ddd, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1.3 Hz, 2H, H9), 7.30 (ddd, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 4.8 Hz, 1.0 Hz, 1H, C2) ppm; ¹³C NMR (101

MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 155.4 (C5), 149.7 (C1), 149.1 (C6), 136.3 (C3), 130.7 (C7), 129.8 (C10), 129.7 (C9), 128.7 (C8), 123.1 (C2), 121.1 (C4) ppm (without signals of perfluorinated aromatic ring); ¹⁹F NMR (376)MHz, CDCl₃) δ: -156.14 (dddd, *J* = 23.3 Hz, 6.3 Hz, 4.5 Hz, 2.7 Hz, 2F, F12), -163.3 (m, 2F, F13) -166.68 (dddd, *J* = 21.90 Hz, 21.84 Hz, 4.3 Hz, 4.3 Hz, 1F, F14) ppm; IR: $\tilde{\nu}_{\max}$ 3331 (w, N-H), 3060 (w, C-H), 1655 (w), 1568 (w), 1521 (s), 1427 (s), 1200 (s), 1117 (s), 1032 (s), 970 (s), 947 (s), 790 (s), 710 (s), 565 (s) cm⁻¹.

2-((4-nitrophenyl)-(2-(perfluorophenyl)hydrazinylidene)methyl)pyridine (2)

Synthetic procedure A: Hydrazones (*E*)-2 and (*Z*)-2 were isolated from crude reaction mixture by flash chromatography (SiO₂, DCM); **overall yield 217 mg (82 %)**, isomers isolated in ratio 1.2 : 1 (*Z* : *E*).

(*Z*)-2, (118 mg) yellow solid, m.p. = 184-188 °C; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 13.03 (bs, 1H, H11), 8.85 (ddd, *J* = 4.9 Hz, 1.7 Hz, 0.8 Hz, 1H, H1), 8.28 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H, H9), 8.03 (ddd, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 7.84 Hz, 1.8 Hz, 1H, H3), 7.75 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 2H, H8), 7.59 (ddd, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 4.9 Hz, 1.0 Hz, 1H, H2), 7.42 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H, H4) ppm, ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 13.55 (s, 1H, H11), 8.80 (d, *J* = 4.6 Hz, 1H, H1), 8.27 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H, H9), 7.85 (ddd, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 7.9 Hz, 1.6 Hz, 1H, H3), 7.77 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H, H8), 7.42 (dd, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 5.2 Hz, 1H, H2), 7.36 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H, H4) ppm, ¹³C NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 152.2 (C5), 148.0 (C1), 147.5 (C10), 144.4 (C7), 139.6 (C6), 137.4 (C3), 129.4 (C8), 124.7 (C4), 123.9 (C2), 123.7 (C9) ppm (without signals of perfluorinated aromatic ring), ¹⁹F NMR (564 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: -156.42 (dddd, *J* = 20.7 Hz, 4.2 Hz, 4.2 Hz, 2.3 Hz, 2F, F12), -163.41 (ddd, *J* = 21.2 Hz, 21.2 Hz, 5 Hz, 2F, F13) -166.72 (dddd, *J* = 21.84 Hz, 21.84 Hz, 4.18 Hz, 4.18 Hz, 1F, F14) ppm, IR : $\tilde{\nu}_{\max}$ 1739 (w), 1574 (w), 1508 (m), 1342 (m), 1216 (m), 1138 (m), 974 (s), 861 (s), 796 (s), 697 (s), 566 (m) cm⁻¹; HRMS (ESI): *m/z* for C₁₈H₉F₅N₄O₂⁺ ([M + H]⁺) found 409.0717; calcd. C₁₈H₉F₅N₄O₂⁺ ([M + H]⁺) 409.0718.

(*E*)-2, (99 mg) yellow solid, m.p. = 145-147 °C; ¹H NMR ((400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 8.40-8.38 (m, 3H, H1, H9), 8.10 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H, H4), 7.69 (ddd, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 7.7 Hz, 1.8 Hz, 1H, H3), 7.54 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H, H8), 7.17 (ddd, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 5.0 Hz, 1.3 Hz, 2H, H2, H11) ppm; ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 154.5 (C5), 148.9 (C1), 148.5 (C10), 147.4 (C7), 137.6 (C6), 136.5 (C3), 130.3 (C8), 124.8 (C9), 123.5 (C2), 120.8 (C4) ppm; ¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: -155.72 (dddd, *J* = 20.7 Hz, 4.2 Hz, 4.2 Hz, 2.3 Hz, 2F, F12), -162.71 (ddd, *J* = 21.8 Hz, 21.7 Hz, 5.0 Hz, 2F, F13) -165.01 (dddd, *J* = 21.79 Hz, 21.79 Hz, 3.62 Hz, 3.62 Hz, 1F, F14) ppm; IR : $\tilde{\nu}_{\max}$ 3335 (w, N-H), 2922 (w, C-H), 1707 (w), 1663 (w), 1593 (w), 1564 (w), 1513 (s), 1425 (m), 1427 (m), 1347 (s), 1201 (s), 1032 (s), 969 (s), 942 (s), 847 (s), 788 (s), 690 (s), 565 (s) cm⁻¹.

(Z)-N,N-dimethyl-4-((2-(perfluorophenyl)hydrazinylidene)(pyridine-2-yl)methyl)aniline (3)

Synthetic procedure A: Hydrazones (*E*-**3** and *Z*-**3**) were isolated from crude reaction mixture by gradient flash chromatography (SiO₂, DCM→hexanes); **overall yield 237 mg (90%), pure isomers isolated in ratio 1.9 : 1 (*Z* : *E*).**

(*Z*-**3**, (156 mg); yellow solid; m.p. = 195 – 198 °C; ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 12.68 (br, 1H, H13), 8.69 (d, *J* = 4.7 Hz, 1H, H1), 7.73 (ddd, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, 1.6 Hz, 1H, H3), 7.39 (m, 3H, H8, H4), 7.28 (ddd, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 4.9 Hz, 1.0 Hz, H2), 6.66 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H, H9), 2.93 (s, 6H, H11, H12) ppm; ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.4 (C5), 150.7 (C10), 147.7 (C1), 143.9 (C6), 137.0 (C3), 129.6 (C8), 126.0 (C7), 125.7 (C4), 123.3 (C2), 112.0 (C9), 40.4 (C11, C12) ppm (without signals of perfluorinated aromatic ring:); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CD₂Cl₂) δ: 12.82 (bs, 1H, H13), 8.80 (ddd, *J* = 4.9 Hz, 1.8 Hz, 0.9 Hz, 1H, H1), 7.86 (ddd, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 7.8 Hz, 1.8 Hz, 1H, H3), 7.50 - 7.44 (m, 3H, H8, H4), 7.42 (ddd, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 4.9 Hz, 1.1 Hz, 1H, H2), 6.77 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H, H9), 3.03 (s, 6H, H11, H12) ppm; ¹³C NMR (128 MHz, CD₂Cl₂) δ: 153.3 (C5), 150.8 (C10), 147.8 (C1), 144.0 (C6), 138.3 (d, C-F coupling, *J* = 246.0 Hz), 137.99 (d, C-F coupling, *J* = 246.2 Hz), 137.2 (C3), 134.7 (d, C-F coupling, *J* = 244.5 Hz), 129.5 (C8), 125.6 (C4, C7), 123.5 (C2), 121.7 (dddd, *J* = 9.56 Hz, 9.17 Hz, 4.34 Hz, 2.05 Hz) 111.7 (C9), 40.2 (C11, C12) ppm; ¹⁹F NMR (470 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ: -156.79 (d, *J* = 22.5 Hz, 2F, F14), -164.09 – 164.37 (m, 2F, F15), -169.42 (dddd, *J* = 23.4 Hz, 23.4 Hz, 5.1 Hz, 5.1 Hz, 1F, F16) ppm; ¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: -156.94 (d, *J* = 22.4 Hz, 2F, F14), -164.35 (td, *J* = 22.0 Hz, 4.9 Hz, 2F, F15), -169.34 (tt, *J* = 22.1 Hz, 5.2 Hz, 1F, F16) ppm; ¹⁵N NMR (61 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ: 320.7 (N-hydrazone), 304.2 (N-pyridine), 121.7 (NH-hydrazone), 50.2 (N-Me₂) ppm; IR : $\tilde{\nu}_{\max}$ 2888 (w, N-H), 1656 (w), 1613 (w), 1518 (s), 1484 (s), 1439 (m) 1361 (m), 1325 (m), 1190 (m), 1111 (s), 1026 (s), 1001 (s), 971 (s), 825 (s), 792 (s), 727 (m) cm⁻¹; HRMS (ESI): *m/z* for C₂₀H₁₅F₅N₄⁺ ([M + H]⁺) found 407.1290; calcd. C₂₀H₁₅F₅N₄⁺ ([M + H]⁺) 407.1288. Main signal corresponds to demethylated fragment C₁₉H₁₃F₅N₄⁺ ([M + H]⁺) found 393.1133, calcd. C₁₉H₁₃F₅N₄⁺ ([M + H]⁺) 393.1133.

(E)-N,N-dimethyl-4-((2-(perfluorophenyl)hydrazinylidene)(pyridine-2-yl)methyl)aniline (3)

(E)-**3**, (34 mg); pale yellow solid; m.p. = 160 – 162 °C; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 8.49 (ddd, J = 4.9 Hz, 1.8 Hz, 1.0 Hz, 1H, H1), 7.96 (ddd, J = 8.1 Hz, 1.8 Hz, 1.1 Hz, 1H, H4), 7.65 (br, 1H, H13), 7.62 (ddd, J = 8.1 Hz, 8.1 Hz, 1.7 Hz, 1H, H3), 7.20 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H, H8), 7.12 (ddd, J = 8.1 Hz, 4.8 Hz, 1.1 Hz, 1H, H2), 6.79 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H, H9), 2.97 (s, 6H, H11, H12) ppm, $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 156.1 (C5), 151.0 (C10), 150.3 (C6), 149.1 (C1), 136.1 (C3), 129.9 (C8), 122.8 (C4), 121.5 (C2), 117.1 (C7), 112.6 (C9), 40.2 (C11, C12) ppm (without signals of perfluorinated aromatic ring); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ : 8.51 (ddd, J = 4.7, 1.8, 0.9 Hz, 1H, H1), 8.10 (dd, J = 8.0, 1.0 Hz, 1H, H4), 7.78 - 7.72 (m, 2H, H3, H13), 7.27 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H, H8), 7.25 (ddd, J = 4.8, 2.6, 1.2 Hz, 1H, H2), 6.90 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H, H9) 3.03 (s, 6H, H11, H12) ppm, $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (128 MHz, CD_2Cl_2) δ : 156.2 (C5), 153.26 (C10), 151.0 (C6), 148.7 (C1), 136.1 (C3), 129.9 (C8), 122.9 (C2), 121.1 (C4), 117.1 (C7), 112.3 (C9), 40,0 (C12, C11) ppm (without signal of perfluorinated ring); $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (470 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ : -154.25 (d, J = 23.6 Hz), -164.09 -164.37 (m), -166.78 (dd, J = 22.3, 22.3 Hz, 1F) ppm; $^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : -156.19 - -156.29 (m, 2F, F14), -163.58- -163.71 (m, 2F, F15), -167.66 (dddd, J = 22.0, Hz, 22.2 Hz, 4.7 Hz, 4.7 Hz, 1F, F16) ppm; IR : $\tilde{\nu}_{\text{max}}$ 3310 (w, N-H), 2959 (w), 2088 (w), 1614 (m, C=N), 1515 (s), 1464 (m) 1427 (m), 1375 (m), 1234 (w), 1118 (m), 1030 (s), 945 (m), 802 (s), 789 (s), 742 (m) cm^{-1} .

Figure S1 ¹H NMR spectrum (600 MHz) of hydrazone (Z)-1 in DMSO-d₆ at 298.15 K.

Figure S2 ¹³C NMR spectrum (151 MHz) of hydrazone 1 E:Z (1:7) mixture in DMSO-d₆ at 298.15 K.

Figure S3 ¹³C NMR spectrum (101 MHz) of hydrazone (Z)-1 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K. (without signals of perfluorinated aromatic ring).

Figure S4 ¹⁹F NMR spectrum (376 MHz) of hydrazone (Z)-1 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K.

Figure S5 ¹H NMR spectrum (600 MHz) of hydrazone (*E*)-1 in DMSO-*d*₆ at 298.15 K.

Figure S6 ¹³C NMR spectrum (101 MHz) of hydrazone (*E*)-1 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K. (without signals of perfluorinated aromatic ring).

Figure S7 ^{19}F NMR spectrum (376 MHz) of hydrazone (E)-1 in CDCl_3 at 298.15 K.

Figure S8 ¹H NMR spectrum (600 MHz) of hydrazone (Z)-2 in DMSO-*d*₆ at 298.15 K.

Figure S9 ¹H NMR spectrum (600 MHz) of hydrazone (Z)-2 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K.

Figure S10 ¹³C NMR spectrum (151 MHz) of hydrazone (Z)-2 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K.

Figure S11 ¹³C NMR spectrum (151 MHz) of hydrazone (Z)-2 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K (no decoupled system).

Figure S12 ¹⁹F NMR spectrum (564 MHz) of hydrazone (Z)-2 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K.

Figure S13 ¹H NMR spectrum (600 MHz) of hydrazone (*E*)-2 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K.

Figure S14 ¹³C NMR spectrum (101 MHz) of hydrazone (*E*)-2 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K. (without signals of perfluorinated aromatic ring).

Figure S15 ¹⁹F NMR spectrum (376 MHz) of hydrazone (E)-2 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K.

Figure S16 ¹H NMR spectrum (600 MHz) of hydrazone (Z)-3 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K.

Figure S17 ¹H NMR spectrum (600 MHz) of hydrazone 3 E:Z (1:9) mixture in CD₂Cl₂ at 298.15 K.

Figure S18 ¹³C DEPT NMR spectrum (126 MHz) of hydrazone 3 *E:Z* (1:9) mixture in CD₂Cl₂ at 298.15 K.

Figure S19 Zoomed ¹³C DEPT NMR spectrum (126 MHz) of hydrazone 3 *E:Z* (1:9) mixture in CD₂Cl₂ at 298.15 K.

Figure S20 ¹³C NMR spectrum (101 MHz) of hydrazone (Z)-3 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K. (without signals of perfluorinated aromatic ring).

Figure S21 COSY NMR spectrum of hydrazone 3 *E:Z* (1:9) mixture in CD₂Cl₂ at 298.15 K.

Figure S22 HSQC NMR spectrum of hydrazone 3 *E:Z* (1:9) mixture in CD₂Cl₂ at 298.15 K.

Figure S23 HMBC NMR spectrum of hydrazone **3** *E:Z* (1:9) mixture in CD₂Cl₂ at 298.15 K

Figure S24 ROESY NMR spectrum of hydrazone **3** *E:Z* (1:9) mixture in CD₂Cl₂ at 298.15 K

Figure S25 ^{19}F NMR spectrum (470 MHz) of hydrazones (*E*)-3 and (*Z*)-3 in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ at 298.15 K.

Figure S26 ^{19}F NMR spectrum (376 MHz) of hydrazone (*Z*)-3 in CDCl_3 at 298.15 K.

Figure S27 ¹H NMR spectrum (600 MHz) of hydrazone (E)-3 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K.

Figure S28 ¹³C NMR spectrum (101 MHz) of hydrazone (E)-3 in CDCl₃ at 298.15 K (without signals of perfluorinated aromatic ring).

Figure S29 ^{19}F NMR spectrum (376 MHz) of hydrazone (E)-3 in CDCl_3 at 298.15 K.

Figure S30 $^{15}\text{N}/^1\text{H}$ HMBC NMR spectrum showing a corresponding interaction between N-H proton of hydrazone (Z)-3 and pyridyl nitrogen (12.30 ppm) as proof of hydrogen bond. Such the interaction is not present in E isomer (8.4 ppm), as a minor isomer present in the sample.

1.2.X-Ray Diffraction on Single Crystalline Material (sc-XRD)

All prepared compounds exhibit hydrazone structural motif, no ESIPT structure was identified. It is necessary to mention that similar triaryl-HZs having the same configuration as *E*-isomers exist,^{3,4} but the structures which resemble suggested ESIPT ones are structurally quite far.^{5,6} In addition, these structural fragments are either a part of 2-pyridyl substituted tetraazaborinine salts or piperidin-2-ylidene substituted phenylazanyl moiety where an azo-hydrazo tautomerism is hard to imagine.

Experimental

The X-ray data for yellow crystals of (*Z*)-**2**, (*E*)-**2** and (*Z*)-**3** were obtained at 150K using Oxford Cryostream low-temperature device with a Bruker D8-Venture diffractometer equipped with Mo (Mo/K_{α} radiation; $\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) microfocus X-ray ($1\mu\text{S}$) source, Photon CMOS detector and Oxford Cryosystems cooling device was used for data collection. Single crystal data collection of (*Z*)-**1** was performed on a STOE diffractometer equipped with Cu (Cu/K_{α} radiation; $\lambda = 1.54059 \text{ \AA}$) microfocus X-ray ($1\mu\text{S}$) source at 100 K. Obtained data were treated by XT-version 2014/5 and SHELXL-2019/1 software implemented in APEX3 v2019.1-0 (Bruker AXS) system.⁷ $R_{\text{int}} = \sum |F_o^2 - F_{o,\text{mean}}^2| / \sum F_o^2$, $S = [\sum (w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2) / (N_{\text{diffrs}} - N_{\text{params}})]^{1/2}$ for all data, $R(F) = \sum | |F_o| - |F_c| | / \sum |F_o|$ for observed data, $wR(F^2) = [\sum (w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2) / (\sum w(F_o^2)^2)]^{1/2}$ for all data. Crystallographic data for all structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC nos. 2331914-2331916 and 2363529. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EY, UK (fax: +44-1223-336033; e-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or [www: http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk](http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk)).

The frames were integrated with the Bruker SAINT software package using a narrow-frame algorithm. Data were corrected for absorption effects using the Multi-Scan method (SADABS). The structures were solved and refined using the Bruker SHELXTL Software Package.

Hydrogen atoms were mostly localized on a difference Fourier map, however to ensure uniformity of treatment of crystal, most of the hydrogen atoms were recalculated into idealized positions (riding model) and assigned temperature factors $\text{Hiso}(\text{H}) = 1.2 \text{ Ueq}$ (pivot atom) or of 1.5 Ueq (methyl). H atoms in methyl moiety and C-H in aromatic rings were placed with C-H distances of 0.97 and 0.93 \AA , respectively. Hydrogen atoms of N-H were placed freely according the maxima on difference Fourier maps, due to strong H-bonding in (*Z*)-**3**, the distances should be restrained below 0.95 \AA . (*Z*)-**3** crystallizes in the form of thin crystals weakly diffracting crystals, which is the reason of slightly higher refinement parameters.

Figure S31 X-ray structure of (*Z*)-**1**, ORTEP (Oak Ridge Thermal Ellipsoid Plot) view – 50% probability, two independent molecules are shown, selected interatomic distances and angles [Å, °]: N1—N2 1.353(3), N4—N5 1.361(3), N1—C1 1.379(3), N4—C19 1.381(3), N2—C7 1.302(3), N5—C25 1.297(3), N3—C12 1.329(3), N6—C30 1.332(3), N3—C8 1.348(3), N6—C26 1.350(3), N2—N1—C1 120.08(19), N5—N4—C19 118.86(18), C7—N2—N1 118.3(2), C25—N5—N4 119.71(19).

Figure S32 Crystal packing of (*Z*)-**1**, view of unit cell along *a*-axis.

Figure S33 Supramolecular architecture of (Z)-1, short contacts are presented with light blue lines.

Figure S34 Hydrogen bonding in (Z)-1, short contacts are presented with light blue lines.

Figure S35 View of the plane defined by the fluorinated phenyl ring in (Z)-1.

Figure S36 View of the interplanar angle of 39.3° defined by the fluorinated phenyl and 2-pyridyl rings in (*Z*)-**1**.

Figure S37 X-ray structure of (*E*)-**2**, ORTEP view – 50% probability, selected interatomic distances and angles [Å, °]: C1—N2 1.2878(19), C1—C2 1.485(2), C1—C7 1.4941(19), O1—N4 1.2277(17), N1—N2 1.3576(18), N1—C13 1.3836(19), C1—N2 1.2878(19), C1—C2 1.485(2), C1—C7 1.4941(19), O1—N4 1.2277(17), N1—N2 1.3576(18), N1—C13 1.3836(19), N2—C1—C2 116.05(13), N2—C1—C7 126.36(13), C2—C1—C7 117.57(12), N2—N1—C13 118.69(13).

Figure S38 Crystal packing of (*E*)-**2**, view of unit cell along *a*-axis.

Figure S39 Supramolecular architecture of (*E*)-**2**, short contacts are presented with light blue lines (two different views).

Figure S40 X-ray structure of (*Z*)-**2**, ORTEP view – 50% probability, selected interatomic distances and angles [Å, °]: C1—N2 1.301(2), C5—C6 1.379(3), C1—C2 1.481(2), C1—C7 1.492(2), N1—N2 1.356(2), N1—C13 1.381(2), O1—N4 1.236(2), O2—N4 1.234(2), C2—N3 1.355(2), N3—C6 1.338(2), N2—C1—C2 127.67(16), N2—C1—C7 112.61(15), C2—C1—C7 119.67(15), N2—N1—C13 119.69(15), C1—N2—N1 119.40 (15), C1—N2—N1 119.40 (15).

Figure S41 Crystal packing of (*Z*)-**2**, view of unit cell along *b*-axis.

Figure S42 Supramolecular architecture of (Z)-2, short contacts are presented with light blue lines.

Figure S43 X-ray structure of (*Z*)-**3**, ORTEP view – 50% probability, two independent molecules are shown, selected interatomic distances and angles [\AA , $^\circ$]: C1—N2 1.286(6), C1—C2 1.481(6), C5'—C6' 1.386(7), C1—C7 1.489(6), N1—N2 1.359(5), N1—C15 1.383(6), C1'—N2' 1.304(6), C1'—C2' 1.483(6), C1'—C7' 1.488(6), N1'—N2' 1.359(6), N1'—C15' 1.385(6), C2'—N3' 1.363(6), C2'—C6' 1.387(7), C2—N3 1.368(6), C2—C6 1.402(6), N3'—C3' 1.334(6), C3—N3 1.329(6), N2—C1—C2 127.3(4), N2—C1—C7 113.4(4), C2—C1—C7 119.3(4), N2'—C1'—C2' 127.3(4), N2'—C1'—C7' 112.4(4), C2'—C1'—C7' 120.3(4), C1—N2—N1 120.2(4), N2'—C1'—C2' 127.3(4), N2'—C1'—C7' 112.4(4), C2'—C1'—C7' 120.3(4), C1'—N2'—N1' 119.4(4).

Figure S44 Crystal packing of (*Z*)-**3**, view of unit cell along *a*-axis.

Figure S45 Supramolecular architecture of (Z)-3, short contacts are presented with light blue lines.

Table S1 Experimental details for (Z)-1

Crystal data	
Chemical formula	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ F ₅ N ₃
<i>M_r</i>	363.29
Crystal system, space group	Triclinic, <i>P</i> -1
Temperature (K)	100
<i>a</i> , <i>b</i> , <i>c</i> (Å)	7.0741(2), 12.4122(3), 17.4750(5)
α, β, γ (°)	94.690(2), 93.783(2), 98.167(2)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1509.06(7)
<i>Z</i>	4
Radiation type	Cu <i>K</i> α
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.23
Crystal size (mm)	0.30 × 0.08 × 0.06
Data collection	
Diffractometer	STOE STADIVARI
Absorption correction	Multi-scan STOE LANA, absorption correction by scaling of reflection intensities. J. Koziskova, F. Hahn, J. Richter, J. Kozisek, "Comparison of different absorption corrections on the model structure of tetrakis(μ ₂ -acetato)- diaqua-di-copper(II)", Acta Chimica Slovaca, vol. 9, no. 2, 2016, pp. 136 - 140.
<i>T_{min}</i> , <i>T_{max}</i>	0.911, 0.982
No. of measured, independent and observed [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)] reflections	40563, 5424, 5230
<i>R_{int}</i>	0.049
(sin θ/λ) _{max} (Å ⁻¹)	0.605
Refinement	
<i>R</i> [<i>F</i> ² > 2σ(<i>F</i> ²)], <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²), <i>S</i>	0.100, 0.264, 1.04
No. of reflections	5424
No. of parameters	549
H-atom treatment	All H-atom parameters refined
Δρ _{max} , Δρ _{min} (e Å ⁻³)	1.58, -0.55

Computer programs: *SHELXL2019/1* (Sheldrick, 2019).

Hydrogen bonding notation [Å, °]: D-H...A; d(D-H); d(H..A); <DHA; d(D..A); symmetry used for intermolecular HB - N1-H1...N3; 0.987; 1.886; 137.76; 2.699, C11-H11...F7; 0.916; 2.608; 129.74; 3.271; [x-1, y+1, z-1], N4-H4...N6; 0.980; 1.953; 125.27; 2.643.

Table S2 Experimental details for (Z)-2

Crystal data	
Chemical formula	C ₁₈ H ₉ F ₅ N ₄ O ₂
<i>M_r</i>	408.29
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, <i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>c</i>
Temperature (K)	150
<i>a</i> , <i>b</i> , <i>c</i> (Å)	15.8169 (8), 6.9386 (3), 15.9805 (7)
β (°)	109.897 (2)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1649.12 (13)
<i>Z</i>	4
Radiation type	Mo Kα
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.15
Crystal size (mm)	0.39 × 0.28 × 0.15
Data collection	
Diffractometer	Bruker D8 - Venture
Absorption correction	Multi-scan <i>SADABS2016/2</i> - Bruker AXS area detector scaling and absorption correction
<i>T_{min}</i> , <i>T_{max}</i>	0.664, 0.746
No. of measured, independent and observed [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)] reflections	39285, 4089, 2687
<i>R_{int}</i>	0.107
(sin θ/λ) _{max} (Å ⁻¹)	0.667
Refinement	
<i>R</i> [<i>F</i> ² > 2σ(<i>F</i> ²)], <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²), <i>S</i>	0.049, 0.111, 1.02
No. of reflections	4089
No. of parameters	267
H-atom treatment	H atoms treated by a mixture of independent and constrained refinement
Δρ _{max} , Δρ _{min} (e Å ⁻³)	0.31, -0.23

Computer programs: Bruker Instrument Service vV6.2.3, *APEX4* v2021.4-1 (Bruker AXS), *SAINT* V8.40B (Bruker AXS Inc., 2019), *SHELXT* 2018/2 (Sheldrick, 2014), *SHELXL2019/1* (Sheldrick, 2019), Bruker *SHELXTL*.

Hydrogen bonding notation [Å, °]: D-H...A; d(D-H); d(H...A); <DHA; d(D..A); symmetry used for intermolecular HB - N1-H1...N3; 0.874; 1.945; 135.09; 2.637, C3-H3...O1; 0.950; 2.607; 142.12; 3.407; [-x+2, -y+1, -z+1], C5-H5...F2; 0.950; 2.454; 144.00; 3.270; [-x+1, y-1/2, -z+3/2], C9-H9...F3; 0.950; 2.474; 160.85; 3.385; [-x+1, y-1/2, -z+1/2], C6-H6...F5; 0.950; 2.632; 161.50; 3.545; [x, -y+3/2, z+1/2].

Table S3 Experimental details for (*E*)-2.

Crystal data	
Chemical formula	C ₁₈ H ₉ F ₅ N ₄ O ₂
<i>M_r</i>	408.29
Crystal system, space group	Triclinic, <i>P</i> -1
Temperature (K)	150
<i>a</i> , <i>b</i> , <i>c</i> (Å)	7.9053 (3), 10.5035 (3), 10.6186 (4)
α , β , γ (°)	71.604 (1), 88.239 (2), 77.415 (1)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	815.85 (5)
<i>Z</i>	2
Radiation type	Mo <i>K</i> α
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.15
Crystal size (mm)	0.24 × 0.23 × 0.12
Data collection	
Diffractometer	Bruker D8 - Venture
Absorption correction	Multi-scan <i>SADABS2016/2</i> - Bruker AXS area detector scaling and absorption correction
<i>T_{min}</i> , <i>T_{max}</i>	0.683, 0.746
No. of measured, independent and observed [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)] reflections	24671, 4056, 3123
<i>R_{int}</i>	0.043
(sin θ/λ) _{max} (Å ⁻¹)	0.667
Refinement	
<i>R</i> [<i>F</i> ² > 2σ(<i>F</i> ²)], <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²), <i>S</i>	0.044, 0.112, 1.03
No. of reflections	4056
No. of parameters	266
H-atom treatment	H atoms treated by a mixture of independent and constrained refinement
$\Delta\rho_{\max}$, $\Delta\rho_{\min}$ (e Å ⁻³)	0.35, -0.28

Computer programs: Bruker Instrument Service vV6.2.3, *APEX4* v2021.4-1 (Bruker AXS), *SAINT* V8.40B (Bruker AXS Inc., 2019), *SHELXT* 2018/2 (Sheldrick, 2014), *SHELXL2019/1* (Sheldrick, 2019), Bruker *SHELXTL*.

Hydrogen bonding notation [Å, °]: D-H...A; d(D-H); d(H..A); <DHA; d(D..A); symmetry used for intermolecular HB - N1-H1...O1; 0.834; 2.388; 172.22; 3.216; [-x, -y+1, -z+2], C6-H6...F2; 0.950; 2.527; 126.76; 3.188; [-x+2, -y+1, -z+1], C9-H9...F1; 0.950; 2.549; 118.45; 3.116; [x-1, y, z].

Table S4 Experimental details for (Z)-3.

Crystal data	
Chemical formula	C ₄₀ H ₃₀ F ₁₀ N ₈
<i>M_r</i>	812.72
Crystal system, space group	Triclinic, <i>P</i> -1
Temperature (K)	150
<i>a</i> , <i>b</i> , <i>c</i> (Å)	9.6295 (5), 9.7463 (5), 18.6889 (10)
α , β , γ (°)	87.454 (2), 87.184 (2), 86.341 (2)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1746.80 (16)
<i>Z</i>	2
Radiation type	Mo <i>K</i> α
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.13
Crystal size (mm)	0.27 × 0.19 × 0.08
Data collection	
Diffractometer	Bruker D8 - Venture
Absorption correction	Multi-scan <i>SADABS2016/2</i> - Bruker AXS area detector scaling and absorption correction
<i>T_{min}</i> , <i>T_{max}</i>	0.652, 0.745
No. of measured, independent and observed [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)] reflections	45240, 6824, 5616
<i>R_{int}</i>	0.058
(sin θ/λ) _{max} (Å ⁻¹)	0.617
Refinement	
<i>R</i> [<i>F</i> ² > 2σ(<i>F</i> ²)], <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²), <i>S</i>	0.093, 0.255, 1.10
No. of reflections	6824
No. of parameters	536
No. of restraints	2
H-atom treatment	H atoms treated by a mixture of independent and constrained refinement $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.079P)^2 + 10.2937P]$ where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$
$\Delta\rho_{\max}$, $\Delta\rho_{\min}$ (e Å ⁻³)	0.79, -0.41

Computer programs: Bruker Instrument Service vV6.2.3, *APEX4* v2021.4-1 (Bruker AXS), *SAINT* V8.40B (Bruker AXS Inc., 2019), *SHELXT* 2018/2 (Sheldrick, 2014), *SHELXL2019/1* (Sheldrick, 2019), Bruker *SHELXTL*.

Hydrogen bonding notation [Å, °]: D-H...A; d(D-H); d(H..A); <DHA; d(D..A); symmetry used for intermolecular HB - N1-H1...N3; 0.952; 1.828; 138.62; 2.618; N1'-H2...N3'; 0.952; 1.847; 134.82; 2.607; C4-H4...F3; 0.950; 2.637; 162.45; 3.554; [x+1, y-1, z].

1.3.X-Ray powder diffraction (powder-XRD)

Self-assembled constructions that converge to thermodynamic equilibrium represent attractive objects for scientific studies. However, sometimes the kinetic pathways can lead to completely dissimilar X-Ray diffraction patterns observed for the micro- and macrocrystals and the two polymorphs can significantly differ in the desired photochemical response.⁸ To compare the prepared powder microcrystals and the thermodynamically driven macrocrystals for single crystal X-Ray diffraction, we performed the XRD analysis of Z-isomers of hydrazones **2** and **3** and compare these spectra with the simulated XRD pattern (in Mercury 4.0)⁹ based on unit-cell parameters from a single crystal X-ray diffraction (Figure 3 in the main text and Figure S46). As shown in Figure S46, the change in diffraction pattern at approximately 150°C indicates the transformation of the (Z)-**2** into the second less stable polymorph (well corresponding to the DSC data - Figure S48 right), contrary to the hydrazone (Z)-**3** (Figure 5 in the main text). Further increase in temperature leads in both cases to melting (broad diffraction halo 10 – 26° 2 θ) and final material decomposition and evaporation of volatile products (broad diffraction halo is significantly reduced).

Figure S46 *In-situ* XRD study (top): Evolution of XRD diffraction pattern of (Z)-**2** with increasing temperature (5°C/min): crystalline lattice change (~150 °C) followed by melting (~185 °C) and sample decomposition (~250°C). Experimental and simulated XRD diffraction pattern of (Z)-**2** based on unit-cell parameters from a single crystal X-ray diffraction (bottom).

Experimental

In-situ powder diffraction data were recorded using a D8 Advance diffractometer (Bruker AXS) in symmetrical acquisition mode. The diffractometer was equipped with a parallel goebel mirror in the primary beam and a linear Si-strip detector (LynxEye, Bruker AXS) in the diffracted beam path, Cu α radiation. The sample was linearly heated at the rate of 5 °C/min in ambient atmosphere; weak maximum at $\sim 26.7^\circ 2\theta$ is arising from the sample substrate.

1.4.DSC, TGA analysis

The results are summarized in Figures S47 and S48. The initial endotherms of (Z)-1 and (Z)-3 powders strongly suggest melting of the material (corresponding melting points are for convenience shown by arrows). In the case of the (Z)-2 powder, we observed an unusual melting peak complexity. After additional *in-situ* XRD analysis (Figure S46), we connected this behavior to a crystalline lattice-change due to the formation of thermodynamically less stable polymorph. Only after the polymorphic change, the (Z)-2 sample starts to melt (~ 185 °C; Figure S47). Due to the transformations' overlap, a determination of the correct melting temperature would be eventually possible only after deconvolution. The molten state is followed by complete decomposition and evaporation of the volatile products documented by the exothermic peak, which is characteristic for each powder material. The phase change and consecutive melting of the studied materials is not directly bound to weight change visible on the TGA traces, only the thermal decomposition and evaporation is readily visible.

Figure S47 Combined DSC/TGA plots for (Z)-1 and (Z)-2 powders. Linear heating, 5 °C/min.

Figure S48 Combined DSC/TGA plots for (Z)-3 powder. Linear heating, 5 °C/min.

Experimental

Thermal analysis of the hydrazone powders was conducted by the means of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, PE Diamond) accompanied by thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA, PE TGA7). The studied material was linearly heated at the rate of 5 °C/min to 400°C under dynamic Ar atmosphere with the flow rate set to ~40 ml/min. Samples for DSC measurements were encapsulated in standard Al pans, TGA sample pan was an open freely hanging Pt pan without cover.

1. Photoswitching in a solvent environment

The photochromic properties of triaryl-HZs were determined by basic and advanced spectroscopic techniques. It is clear from attached data, that the triaryl-HZs possess poor photochromic properties in solution. Nevertheless, the basic photochromic properties were determined for comprehensive understanding of their behavior in solution.

2.1. UV-Vis spectroscopy

2.1.1. Generals

Experimental

UV-Vis absorption spectra were obtained on an Agilent 8453 diode array spectrophotometer (Hewlett Packard, USA) in HPLC or UV-spectroscopy grade solvent (toluene, Acros Organics). Solvents used on NMR-spectroscopy measurements (toluene – Acros Organics, deuterated CD_2Cl_2 – Eurisotop-France, toluene- d_8 , Eurisotop-France). All solvents were used without further purification.

Quantitative photochemical measurements for determination of photoisomerization quantum yields in solution were performed at 25°C in the dark, with either UV-glass window 315 nm LED diode (LED315W; Thorlabs; Figure S49); or epoxy-encased 405 nm diode (LED405E; Thorlabs; Figure S50). Irradiation of powders was carried out using 365 nm LED array light source (LIU365A, Thorlabs, Figure S51).

Figure S49 Typical spectral intensity distribution of used 315 nm LED diode with UV-glass window (LED315W; Thorlabs; <https://www.thorlabs.com/thorproduct.cfm?partnumber=LED315W> (accessed January 16, 2024)).

Figure S50 Typical spectral (left) and radial (right) intensity distribution of used 405 nm epoxy-encased LED diode (LED405E, Thorlabs; <https://www.thorlabs.com/thorproduct.cfm?partnumber=LED405E> (accessed January 16, 2024)).

Figure S51 Typical spectral intensity distribution of used 365 nm LED array light source (LIU365A, Thorlabs; <https://www.thorlabs.com/thorproduct.cfm?partnumber=LIU365A> (accessed January 16, 2024)).

The light sources were three 315nm, four 405nm LED diodes Thorlabs with overall incident light intensity of $I_0=1.69\pm0.10\times10^{-6}$ mol s⁻¹ dm⁻³ and $I_0=4.2\pm0.2\times10^{-5}$ mol s⁻¹ dm⁻³, respectively. The incident light intensity I_0 at 315 nm ($I_{0\ 315}$) and I_0 at 405 nm ($I_{0\ 405}$) were determined by ferrioxalate (FE) actinometry in our previous work.²

2.1.1. Photochromic behavior in solution

Figure S52 UV-Vis absorption spectra of **1** (5 × 10⁻⁵ M) with PSS states in toluene. PSS_{315 nm} UV-Vis spectrum was obtained upon 315 nm light irradiation for 5 min. PSS_{370 nm} UV-Vis spectrum was obtained upon 370 nm light irradiation for 20 min.

Figure S53 UV-Vis absorption spectra of **2** (5 × 10⁻⁵ M) with their PSS states in toluene. PSS_{315 nm} UV-Vis spectrum was obtained upon 315 nm light irradiation for 12 min. PSS_{370 nm} UV-Vis spectrum was obtained upon 370 nm light irradiation for 15 min.

Figure S54 UV-Vis absorption spectra of **3** (5×10^{-5} M) with their PSS states in toluene. PSS_{315 nm} UV-Vis spectrum was obtained upon 315 nm light irradiation for 8 min. PSS_{405 nm} UV-Vis spectrum was obtained upon 405 nm light irradiation for 13 min.

Table S5 Photochromic properties for triaryl-HZs **1 – 3**

Hydrazone	$\varepsilon/\lambda_{\max}$	$\varepsilon/\lambda_{\max}$	Φ		PSS (<i>E</i> : <i>Z</i>)	
	<i>E</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>Z</i>
1	23100 / 317	18500 / 358	0.5 (15)	0.01 (2)	2 : 98	9 : 91
2	26400 / 306	22400 / 372	12.3(21)	0.8(3)	3 : 97	49 : 51
3	23100 / 309	13600 / 381	3.3 (10)	0.025(2)	7 : 93	25 : 75

ε – molar absorption (extinction) coefficient (in $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$); λ_{\max} – UV/Vis absorption maximum (in nm); Φ – quantum yield of photoisomerization (in %); PSS – photostationary state composition at the corresponding irradiation wavelength (in %).

Methods

The *E*-to-*Z* (or *Z*-to-*E*) differential photoisomerization quantum yield (Φ) was determined by equation (S1) at low photoconversion conditions (to avoid photoproduct absorption and thus eliminate the effect of back photoisomerization)¹⁰:

$$\Phi = \frac{\int_{c_0}^{c_t} dc}{\int_0^t I_a dt} = \frac{\Delta c}{\int_0^t I_a dt} \quad (\text{S1})$$

where: Δc is the concentration change of the *Z* isomer (an increase for the *E*-to-*Z* and a decrease for the *Z*-to-*E* photoisomerization), I_a is absorbed light intensity by the initial isomer at the irradiation wavelength λ using a monochromatic light source, and t is the irradiation time. Because we started with a pure isomer (with a known extinction coefficient) and the long-wavelength absorption band of all studied *Z* isomers was sufficiently separated from the corresponding *E* isomer, the concentration change Δc can be easily determined spectrophotometrically. The photoisomerization quantum yields of the triaryl-HZ **1** were determined in our previous works.^{1,2}

The absorbed light intensity I_a at the corresponding irradiation wavelengths λ was determined using a Thorlabs PM16-140 – USB Power Meter (Integrating Sphere Sensor, FC Fiber Adapter, Si, 350 – 1100 nm, 500 mW Max) or an Ocean Optics HR4000CG-UV-NIR spectrophotometer (for the wavelength of 315 nm) by Eq. (S2):

$$I_{a\lambda} = I_{0\lambda} - I_{T\lambda} \quad (\text{S2})$$

The accuracy of determining the quantum yields was verified by the comparison of photostationary state (PSS) composition obtained by ^1H NMR spectroscopy and that calculated from Eq. (S3)¹¹:

$$\frac{[E]}{[Z]} = \frac{\varepsilon_Z \Phi_{Z \rightarrow E}}{\varepsilon_E \Phi_{E \rightarrow Z}} \quad (\text{S3})$$

where: $[X]$ is the concentration of the corresponding isomer X in the PSS, ε_X is the molar absorption (extinction) coefficient of the isomer X and $\Phi_{X \rightarrow Y}$ is the photoisomerization quantum yield of the X -to- Y photoisomerization.

The depicted half-lives in Table S6 clearly indicate that the thermal back-reaction can be neglected during the photochemical quantum yield determination.

2.2. NMR spectroscopy

2.2.1. General

Experimental

Variable temperature NMR spectra (183.15 K – 298.15 K) were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE II spectrometer with a triple resonance broad-band probe (5 mm TBO BB-1H/19F/D Z-GRD) operating at 499.9 MHz for ^1H and 125.7 MHz for ^{13}C . ^{15}N NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer with an inverse triple resonance cryo probe with an ATM module (5 mm CPTCI $^1\text{H}/^{13}\text{C}/^{15}\text{N}/\text{D}$ Z-GRD) operating at 600.1 MHz for ^1H , 150.9 MHz for ^{13}C and 60.8 MHz for ^{15}N . For NMR signal assignment in solution, standard Bruker pulse sequences for 1D (^1H , ^{13}C -APT) and 2D (COSY, ROESY, HSQC, HMBC) NMR experiments at a corrected temperature of 298 K were employed, measuring all samples in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$. Liquid-state NMR data were interpreted using Topspin 3.5 and references to the solvent signals: $\text{DMSO-}d_6$: $\delta=2.50$ (^1H) and $\delta=39.7$ ppm (^{13}C).

2.2.1. Temperature dependence

Basic ^1H NMR measurement at various lower temperatures showed, that no third form (potential PT_2 -like form) is present in solution. Better separation of the peaks at lower temperature for similar structures if they are present in the sample at lower temperature was considered (Figure S55). As the temperature dropped down, the shift of the N–H proton of the Z isomer to higher ppm was the only observation (Figure S56).

Figure S55 ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz) of hydrazone **3** (Z:E, 90:10) in CD_2Cl_2 at various temperatures (298.15 K – 183.15 K). No significant changes of isomers' ratio were detected. No new signals (new tautomeric form) were detected with decreasing temperature only shifting of the hydrazone functional group proton signal (N–H) to higher ppm.

Figure S56 ¹H NMR spectra (500 MHz) of hydrazone **3** (*Z*:*E*, 90:10) in CD₂Cl₂ at various temperatures (298.15-183.15 K). Intensity and positions of the signals slightly changed with decreasing temperature. The most significant shift to higher ppm was detected for highlighted protons signal (red coloured hydrogen, change from 12.77 at temperature 298.15 K to 13.03 ppm at 183.15 K). No significant changes of isomers' ratio were detected.

2.2.2. Photoisomerization in solution

In *situ* irradiation in NMR cuvette leads only to $E \rightarrow Z$ isomerization without any formation of the third (PT_2 -like) form (Figure S57).

Experimental

For NMR experiments with *in situ* irradiation, we also used a 365 nm light emitting diode (LED) source (Thorlabs, Germany). The light was guided directly into the NMR tube via a coaxial insert, with a multimode silica optical fiber with 1 mm diameter, 0.39 NA, high amount of OH from Thorlabs, Germany. Irradiation of the sample was applied with a sandblasted silica fiber centred in the central axis of the NMR tube.

Figure S57 ^1H NMR spectra at room temperature (25 °C). Hydrazone **3** $Z \rightarrow E$ photoisomerization in CD_2Cl_2 during irradiation by UV light (365 nm, 60 min) left and $E \rightarrow Z$ photoisomerization (405 nm, 60 min) right. Change of the relative amount of the isomers is showed in middle. According to the data measured by proton NMR spectroscopy, composition of the PSS state is (20:80 - $E:Z$).

2.2.3. Thermal stability in solution

Figure S58 Schematic representation of studied thermal isomerization in solution.

Methods

The rate constants for thermally initiated $E \rightarrow Z$ (k_1) and back $Z \rightarrow E$ (k_{-1}) isomerizations for studied hydrazones were determined using following nonlinear fit equation (describing thermodynamic equilibrium between two isomers at corresponding temperature):

$$x_E(t) = x_{E(\text{eq})} + (x_{E(i)} - x_{E(\text{eq})})e^{-kt} \quad (\text{S4})$$

where:

$$k = k_1 + k_{-1}; \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$k_1 = (1 - x_{E(\text{eq})})k \quad (\text{S6})$$

$$k_{-1} = x_{E(\text{eq})}k \quad (\text{S7})$$

In equations (4)-(7), $x_{E(\text{eq})}$ denotes the relative amount of E isomer in a thermodynamic equilibrium; $x_{E(i)}$ is the initial relative amount of E isomer and t represents the time. The percentage of E isomer was evaluated based on the differences between the relative intensity of the N–H signals among conformers in ^1H NMR spectra (Figure 59; N–H signals in ^1H NMR are narrow and show no sign of being exchanged with water in toluene solvent). In case of visible overlapping between N–H proton signal with other signals, another well-separated signal corresponding to different proton was selected.

All uncertainties were calculated applying the standard error propagation formula for independent variables:

$$\sigma_f = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}\right)^2 \sigma_x^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y}\right)^2 \sigma_y^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial z}\right)^2 \sigma_z^2 + \dots} \quad (\text{S8})$$

Gibbs free energy of transition state, ΔG^\ddagger was designated from Eyring-Polanyi equation, introducing determined isomerization constants:

$$\ln\left(\frac{k_i h}{k_B T}\right) = -\frac{\Delta G^\ddagger}{RT} \gg \Delta G^\ddagger = -RT \ln\left(\frac{k_i h}{k_B T}\right) \quad (\text{S9})$$

where k_B and h denote Boltzmann and Planck constant, respectively. Due to the time-consuming nature of ^1H NMR kinetic experiments, rate constants k_i and activation parameters at room temperature were calculated based on Eyring–Polanyi equation (S9), assuming ΔG^\ddagger does not depend on temperature changes, i.e. $\Delta G^\ddagger = \Delta H^\ddagger$ or $\Delta S^\ddagger = 0$. This approximation is based on our previous study of hydrazone systems^{1,4,5} with both experimentally determined and calculated entropy values which were consistent with this approximation. Therefore, we estimated the uncertainty σS associated with the $\Delta S^\ddagger = 0$ approximation and included it in the total error budget.

The half-time thermal isomerization at room temperature, $t_{1/2}$ was determined using the following formula:

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{\ln 2}{k_i} \quad (\text{S10})$$

where k_i represents rate constant of the corresponding thermal isomerization at 298.15 K.

The equilibrium constants, K_{eq} were calculated from the designated ΔG^\ddagger values at 298.15 K (see eq. S11).

$$K_{\text{eq}} = \frac{x_{Z(\text{eq})}}{x_{E(\text{eq})}} \quad (\text{S11})$$

Figure S59 ^1H NMR of hydrazone (*E*)-**1** in toluene- d_8 at 60 °C during thermal isomerisation. Highlighted signals: growing of a new peak at 13.52 ppm for N–H of *Z* isomer (light grey) and decreasing intensity of the N–H (7.28 ppm) signals of *E* isomer (dark grey).

Figure S60 Thermal *E*→*Z* isomerization of (*E*)-**1** in toluene- d_8 at 333.15 K. The plot is the decreasing relative amount of (*E*)-**1** as a function of time.

Figure S61 Thermal $E \rightarrow Z$ isomerization of (E)-**3** in toluene- d_8 at 333.15 K. The plot is the decreasing relative amount of (E)-**3** as a function of time.

Table S6 Thermal stability of triaryl-HZs **1-3** in toluene (at 25 °C)

Compound	Conf.	k [s ⁻¹]	$\tau_{1/2}$ [years]	ΔG^\ddagger [kcal/mol]	$\Delta_r G$ [kcal/mol]	K_{eq} [Z/E]
1	<i>E</i>	$(2.32 \pm 0.21) \times 10^{-9}$	9.4 ± 0.9	29.23 ± 0.05	-0.88 ± 0.10	4.4 ± 0.7
	<i>Z</i>	$(5.29 \pm 0.75) \times 10^{-10}$	41.6 ± 5.9	30.11 ± 0.08		
2^a	<i>E</i>	$(9.95 \pm 0.49) \times 10^{-9}$	2.21 ± 0.12	28.37 ± 0.30	—	—
3	<i>E</i>	$(7.28 \pm 0.52) \times 10^{-8}$	0.3 ± 0.02	27.19 ± 0.03	-1.02 ± 0.07	5.6 ± 0.6
	<i>Z</i>	$(1.29 \pm 0.12) \times 10^{-8}$	1.7 ± 0.15	28.21 ± 0.04		

^aThermal stability was determined in our previous work²

2. Color changes studies in solid state

3.1. Reflectance spectroscopy

Figure S62 Diffuse reflection spectra of hydrazone **1** (left) and **2** (right) in powder after Kubelka–Munk transformation before (dark) and after UV light irradiation (405 nm).

Figure S63 Thermal stability of powder (Z)-3 at 298.15 K represented by the decreasing Kubelka–Munk reflectance at the new band maximum (516 nm) ($\tau_{1/2} = \ln 2 \times t_1$).

Experimental

Relative reflectance spectra were measured on Jasco V-770 spectrometer with Jasco ARSN917 unit attached. All measurements baselines were corrected on Spectralon reference standard (PN: 6708-H006A). Irradiation of samples was performed directly in ARSN-917 unit (to avoid sample movement) with 405 nm epoxy-encased LED diode (LED405E; Thorlabs). All spectra were processed using Kubelka–Munk conversion.^{12,13}

Figure S64 (Z)-3 powder before (left) and after (right) irradiation in an inert (argon) atmosphere with 405 nm LED array.

3.2. Photoswitching cycles

Figure S65 Photoswitching cycles of the (Z)-2 thin film on glass substrate at 566 nm obtained by alternating the 405 nm LED irradiation (2 min irradiation time) and the back thermal reaction. The back reaction was initiated by heating at 80 °C using a heat gun with temperature control (3 min; 3 cm distance from the sample).

Figure S66 Photoswitching cycles of the (Z)-3 thin film on glass substrate at 533 nm obtained by alternating the 405 nm LED irradiation (2 min irradiation time) and the back thermal reaction. The back reaction was initiated by heating at 80 °C using a heat gun with temperature control (8 min; 3 cm distance from the sample). Due to the long lifetime of the back reaction ($t_{1/2} = 24$ days at ambient temperature), the applied heating period did not lead to the complete transformation to the initial yellow form. Nevertheless, we would like to show the switching ability of the triaryl-HZ (Z)-3.

Experimental

The photoswitching cycles were measured using spin-coated thin film of the hydrazone on the glass slide for optical microscopy (10 mg of the hydrazone (Z)-**2** dissolved in 500 mg of the CH₂Cl₂, w = 2 %). Before deposition, the substrates were ultrasonically cleaned in ethanol and then exposed to an oxygen plasma (O₂ partial pressure 0.2 mbar, RF plasma 80 W) in a vacuum chamber. The drop casted solution was spined at 50 rps in first 3 seconds and then for 80 seconds at 1500 rps. The same procedure was used for preparing the thin film of the hydrazone (Z)-**3**, except for the lower concentration of the (Z)-**3** (w = 0.25 %).

3.3.ss-NMR spectroscopy

Since we did not observe the solid-state (*Z*)-**3** to (*E*)-**3** photoisomerization by any other technique (as shown in Figure S57, the (*Z*)-**3** to (*E*)-**3** photoisomerization is not favored even in solution) and the ESIPT form (PT₂ in the main text) is not photochemically active (only the thermal back-reaction to the initial *Z* isomer occurs), we believe that the minor form observed in the ¹³C CP-MAS spectra (Figure S67) is the second (*Z*)-**3** polymorph which converts completely to the major polymorph upon irradiation.

Figure S67 ¹³C CP-MAS spectra of yellow powder of **3** prior to (black) and after 1 and 7 hours of irradiation by 365 nm. There is an additional set of ¹³C signals in the initial state (with approximately 5% of intensity compared to the major form) disappearing upon irradiation.

The N–H crosspeak (Figure S68) confirms a presence of hydrazo form in both cases. The ¹H chemical shift of 13.7 ppm indicates that the N–H proton is involved in strong intramolecular hydrogen bond, corresponding to the *Z* isomer. The ¹⁴N chemical shift does not agree with the ¹⁵N chemical shift described in literature, when hydrazo form nitrogen resonates at ca. 350 ppm. The reason is that the ¹⁴N chemical shift is influenced by quadrupolar coupling, which should be calculated from the optimized structure and, therefore, the experimental chemical shift should be recalculated.

Figure S68 $^1\text{H},^{14}\text{N}$ - heteronuclear dipolar recoupling experiment (2D-HMQC)¹⁴ of yellow (left) and orange (right) powder of **3**.

Experimental

The solid-state NMR experiments were performed on a Jeol spectrometer with 3.2 mm HX MAS probe operating at 600.2 MHz for ^1H and 150.9 MHz for ^{13}C with a MAS frequency of 12 kHz. ^1H - ^{14}N D-HMQC experiments were recorded on a Jeol spectrometer with 1 mm HX MAS probe operating at 600.2 MHz for ^1H , 150.9 MHz for ^{13}C and 43.4 MHz for ^{14}N with a MAS frequency of 70 kHz and with parameter setup published.¹⁴ The solid-state NMR data were processed and interpreted in MestreNova and Delta 5.3 (Jeol).

3.4. FTIR spectroscopy

FTIR spectroscopy was included to characterize each isomer of studied pentafluoro triaryl-HZs. The spectra of (*Z*)-isomers were measured before and after 405 nm LED irradiation (each powder sample was rummaged and turned over several times to accomplished maximal color change of the material). Changes in peaks intensity, shape and position after irradiation were only negligible in the case of all studied *Z* isomers (as shown in graphs below). The brief analysis of spectra was processed according to our previous work.¹⁵

Experimental

Infrared spectra were recorded at Nicolet 6700 FT-IR (Thermo-Fisher Scientific, USA) spectrometer (ATR technique).

Figure S69 IR spectrum of pentafluorinated triaryl-Hz (*E*)-1 (powder).

Figure S70 IR spectrum of pentafluorinated triaryl-Hz (*Z*)-1 (powder-dark form).

Figure S 71 IR spectrum of pentafluorinated triaryl-Hz (*Z*)-1 (powder-irradiated form).

Figure S72 IR spectrum of pentafluorinated triaryl-Hz (*Z*)-2 (powder-dark form).

Figure S73 IR spectrum of pentafluorinated triaryl-Hz (*Z*)-2 (powder-irradiated form).

Figure S74 IR spectrum of pentafluorinated triaryl-Hz (*E*)-2 (powder).

Figure S75 IR spectrum of pentafluorinated triaryl-Hz (*Z*)-3 (powder-dark form).

Figure S76 IR spectrum of pentafluorinated triaryl-Hz (*Z*)-3 (powder-irradiated form).

Figure S77 IR spectrum of pentafluorinated triaryl-Hz (*E*)-3 (powder).

3.5.EPR spectroscopy

Figure S78 (left) Low intensity EPR spectrum (centered at $g = 2.0043$) of the hydrazone (Z)-3 10 mg powder sample recorded before the continuous irradiation. (right) Low intensity EPR spectrum (centered at $g = 2.0037$) of the hydrazone (Z)-3 10 mg powder sample recorded during the continuous irradiation (365 nm).

Figure S79 In-situ irradiation on Bruker EMX^{plus} 10/12 CW (continuous wave) spectrometer with attached sample of the hydrazone (Z)-3.

Experimental

All the EPR spectra were acquired on *Bruker* EMX^{plus} 10/12 CW (continuous wave) spectrometer equipped with a Premium-X-band microwave bridge. The g_{iso} value of radicals was determined using a built-in spectrometer frequency counter and a ER-036TM NMR-Teslameter (*Bruker*). All g –Values were determined with the precision of ± 0.0002 . Powder samples (≈ 10 mg) were inserted into the quartz-tubes (i. d. = 3 mm) and the following parameters were usually set up to measure the spectra: central field = 348 mT, sweep width = 20 mT, microwave frequency ≈ 9.794 , modulation amplitude = 0.075 mT, resolution (number of points per sweep) = 2267, microwave power = 3.17 mW, modulation frequency = 100 kHz, time constant = 1.28 ms and conversion time = 3.95 ms. Prior to measurement all samples were flushed with N₂ in order to reduce the influence of oxygen on the EPR spectra line-broadening. *In situ* sample irradiation was performed by 365 nm LED (Thorlabs GmbH) where light was brought via an optical cable directly into the EPR tube just (5 – 10) mm above the powder surface (see also design of the NMR irradiation experiment).

3.6. Confocal Raman microscopy

Figure S80 Raman spectra of the hydrazone (E)-1 powder surface before (black) and after (red) irradiation by laser of 355 nm for 3 seconds. No change of the spectra was occurred. However, the slightly different color of the illuminated area by the excitation laser suggests subsurface photodegradation not observed in Raman spectra.

Figure S81 Raman spectra of the hydrazone (Z)-1 powder surface before (black) and after (red) irradiation by laser of 355 nm for 3 seconds. No change in the spectra was observed. The slightly different color of the illuminated area by the excitation laser suggests subsurface photodegradation not observed in Raman spectra.

Figure S82 Raman spectra of the hydrazone (E)-2 powder surface before (black) and after (red) irradiation by laser of 355 nm for 3 seconds. No change of the spectra was occurred.

Figure S83 Raman spectra of the hydrazone (Z)-2 powder surface before (black) and after (red) irradiation by laser of 355 nm for 3 seconds. The formation of the new vibrations was detected in the marked region of 1400-1450 cm^{-1} (the zoomed-in area).

Figure S84 Thermal stability of powder (Z)-2 at 298.15 K. The plot is the decreasing of the relative amount of the new form gained through measuring the specific new signal at 1440 cm^{-1} using confocal Raman spectrometry ($\tau_{1/2} = \ln 2 \times t_1$).

Figure S85 Raman spectra of the hydrazone (E)-3 powder surface before (black) and after (red) irradiation by laser of 355 nm for 3 seconds. No change of the spectra was occurred. However, the slightly different color of the illuminated area by the excitation laser suggests subsurface photodegradation not observed in Raman spectra.

Experimental

Raman measurements were performed with a standard Witec alpha300 R confocal Raman microscope. The excitation wavelength was 786 nm to avoid resonant Raman scattering. The laser beam was focused on powder sample with a 50x objective, and the measured spectra were averaged over an area of 10 mm².

3.7. Langmuir film formation and Langmuir-Schaefer deposition

The Langmuir-Schaeffer deposition technique was used to deposit a thin film of hydrazone (**Z**)-**3** at the surface pressure of 25 mN/m on silicon substrates by slowly removing water from the Langmuir-Blodgett trough. For the purpose of optical absorption measurements, the films were also deposited onto fused silica substrates.

The optical transmission of a thin hydrazone (**Z**)-**3** film deposited on a fused silica substrate is illustrated in Figure S86. Upon illumination with a 365 nm laser beam (fluence 1 mW/cm²) for a few seconds, a distinct change in absorbance within the 450-550 nm range is observed. Heating the film reverses this absorption alteration.

Figure S86 Photoswitching of the thin layer composed of hydrazone (**Z**)-**3** in solid state at room temperature. The thin layer was prepared by Langmuir-Schaefer deposition.

Experimental

A hydrazone (**Z**)-**3** thin film was prepared using the Langmuir-Schaeffer deposition technique. First, hydrazone powder was dissolved in chloroform (Sigma-Aldrich) at a concentration of 4 mg/mL. Then, 450 μ L of this solution was spread onto the air-water interface of a high-compression Langmuir-Blodgett trough (KSV-NIMA). The chloroform was allowed to evaporate for 30 minutes before compressing the Langmuir film. The Wilhelmy plate sensor was used to monitor surface pressure.

The hydrazone molecules were compressed with Teflon barriers until the area reached 103 cm² (initial area 549 cm²), resulting in a final surface pressure of 25 mN/m. The compression speed was maintained at 10 cm²/min (Figure S87). Figure S87 shows the surface pressure-area (Π -A) isotherm of hydrazone Langmuir film, showing distinct interruptions in continuous film compression followed by surface pressure relaxation. X-ray reflectivity (XRR) was measured directly in a trough during these interruptions. With increasing surface pressure, a maximum in XRR data at approx. 0.35 \AA^{-1} indicates the formation of a layered film. By comparing with the GIWAXS reciprocal space map (Figure 12 in the main text), the maximum in XRR can be assigned to the X-ray reflection by 001 planes of hydrazone film.

Figure S87 a) Π - A isotherm of hydrazone 3 Langmuir film. b) XRR curves measured at different Π .

The ex-situ XRR measurement of the final film transferred to a Si substrate at a surface pressure of 25 mN/m is shown in Figure S88. In addition to the Bragg peaks, Kiessig fringes are also present, which can be used to determine the total film thickness of approximately 7.6 nm.

Figure S88 Measured XRR of the molecular film transferred onto a Si substrate.

3.7.1. Grazing-incidence wide-angle X-ray scattering (GIWAXS)

Experimental

GIWAXS measurements (Figure 12 in the main text) were performed using a modified Bruker system (Nanostar) equipped with a metal-jet X-ray source (Excillum) and a 2D X-ray detector (Dectris 300K). The angle of incidence was 0.1 degrees and the distance between sample and detector was 157 mm.

3.8. Crystal structure and proton transfer

3.8.1. Absence of photochromism in molecule **1**

In the molecular model, the energy barrier for the $PT_2 \rightarrow PT_1$ proton transfer in molecule **1** is comparable to that in molecule **3** (7.9 vs. 8.7 kcal/mol at the CCSD(T) level). This suggests that the difference in their photochromic behaviour arises from the crystal structure rather than electronic effects at the single-molecule level.

The crystal structure of molecule **1** contains two distinct forms: one with a shorter intramolecular hydrogen bond and another with a longer one. Molecule **1** in the latter form is thus less likely to undergo the proton transfer due to the longer distance required for the proton to traverse.

Additionally, the photochromism is further suppressed by the crystal embedding of compound **1**. The *Z* crystal structures of all three compounds exhibit a head-to-tail arrangement, likely facilitated by the antiparallel alignment of dipole moments. In molecules **2** and **3**, the perfluorophenyl and pyridyl rings form planes that stack together, interacting via the substituted phenyl groups (T-type stacking in molecule **3** and π - π stacking in molecule **2**). This differs from molecule **1**, where the two different forms display a planar arrangement also between the perfluorophenyl and phenyl groups (in addition to the stacking between perfluorophenyl and pyridyl rings). When the proton transfer to the pyridyl ring occurs in the excited state, the subsequent pyridyl rotation positions is hindered by the steric clash between the hydrogens of the pyridyl and phenyl groups. This repulsive contact is significantly shorter in molecule **1** compared to molecules **2** and **3**, where the rotated substituted phenyl provides more space for the pyridyl rotation. The figure below illustrates the steric clash and the torsion angles of the (substituted) phenyl groups.

Figure S89 Steric clash and the torsion angles of the (substituted) phenyl groups before and upon proton transfer.

3.8.2. Differences in thermal back-reaction for **2** and **3**

There are two possible sources of the difference between **2** and **3**: electronic effects visible already at molecular level and bulk effects which are result of different crystal structure. From CCCSD(T)/def2-TZVPP calculation in toluene we observe 2.9 kcal/mol smaller barrier for PT₂-to-PT₁ transformation of **2** in comparison with **3** - which is the rate limiting step. Our models do not allow for direct estimation of the barrier in solid state, but due to steric clashes it is plausible to expect larger barrier. If we take experimental half-life of 24 days (**3**) we obtain barrier of 26.5 kcal/mol. Decreasing it by calculated molecular effect of 2.9 kcal/mol gives barrier of 23.6 kcal/mol which corresponds to half-life of 4.8 hours close to experimental value for **2** - 36 minutes (barrier 22.3 kcal/mol). The molecular orientation in crystals of **2** and **3** is similar we can thus roughly approximate that main factor behind the change in thermal stability are electronic effects observable already at the molecular level followed by steric factors.

In both PT₂ cases (**2**, **3**) we see that the substituted phenyl is rotated out of the conjugation with the rest of system. Transition state features opposite situation with protonated pyridyl perpendicular to the plane created by two remaining cycles. Both PT₂ and corresponding transition state are structures with high polarity. Combination of two strong electron withdrawing groups (perfluorophenyl and nitrophenyl) in **2** further weakens formally double bond between C=C(pyridyl) and facilitates rotation. This is true also for other isomerization when comparing **2** and **3**.

3. Computational study

4.1. Computational details

Three different strategies were applied in this study. First, the range-separated ω B97XD functional¹⁶ was used as it is appropriate for describing various types of electronic transitions including charge transfer states as well as dispersion interactions. Solvent effects of toluene were included by implicit SMD solvent model.¹⁷ Triple-zeta def2-TZVPP basis¹⁸ set was used in Gaussian 16 software. Different initial geometries were used to reach optimized isomer structures. Geometry optimizations were always followed by frequency calculation, and no imaginary frequency was found for the reported minima. Raman spectra were calculated in Gaussian at the same level of theory. Next, frequencies (Raman shifts) were scaled by factor (0.95 def2-SVP, 0.98 def2-TZVPP) to account for known systematic errors in the harmonic approximation. Raman activities were converted to intensities¹⁹ assuming a temperature of 298 K and 532 nm incident laser source using Chemcraft software.²⁰ All peaks were broadened using Gaussian functions with FWHM equal to 4 cm^{-1} . To compare with experimental observations, we modelled different compositions of a mixture containing the Z and proton-transferred structure (PT₂). Raman spectrum of the mixture was obtained by summing the weighted spectra of the Z and PT₂. Electronic absorption spectrum was approximated as vertical excitations in optimized geometries. Since our initial calculations showed that the ω B97XD excitation energies are significantly blue shifted compared to experimental Z isomer absorption maxima we switched to the PBE0 functional.²¹ Single point ground-state DLPNO-CCSD(T)/def2-TZVPP calculations^{22–30} were performed in ORCA 5.0.4 software³¹ using TightPNO settings.

Excited state transformations were studied in gas phase applying the Mixed-Reference Spin-Flip (MRSF)^{32,33} approach using the BHHLYP functional, in-built double-zeta quality basis set 6-31G(d), ultrafine-like integration grid and restricted-open shell reference for spin-flip. Minimal energy conical intersections were searched³⁴ using the branching plane updating method.³⁵ We have found that Rational Function Optimization algorithm selection improves convergence. All MRSF calculations were performed with Gamess software version 30 Sep. 2022 (R2).³⁶

Solid-state effects were approached by modelling larger clusters of Z isomers cut from the experimental crystal structure as well as by periodic boundary conditions (PBC) calculations. In the finite-size calculations, four molecules were used as a minimal model. The same methodology was applied as above but smaller def2-SVP basis set was used. During the geometry optimization, the pyridine and the CNNH moieties of one of the molecules were allowed to relax together with all hydrogens in all four molecules, while all the remaining atoms were kept frozen. A proton transferred structure was modelled by moving proton to the respective pyridine and its rotation as in PT₂ (see Figure S89). Again, hydrogens in all molecules, protonated pyridine and hydrazone moiety in PT structure were only allowed to relax. The optimized structures were used to simulate absorption spectra.

The periodic DFT calculations were performed using the projector-augmented wave method implemented in the Vienna ab-initio simulation package (VASP) suite.^{37,38} The structures and lattice parameters of the system were created from the *cif* files obtained experimentally via XRD. The energy cut-off for the plane-wave expansion was set to 500 eV, and the 3×3×3 *k*-point grid was used to sample the Brillouin zone of the supercell. We used the optimized van der Waals DFT functional optB86b-

vdW³⁹ which has recently demonstrated very balanced description of covalent, van der Waals and hydrogen bonding on a test set of various polymorphs of ice.⁴⁰ The geometries of both crystalline lattice and atomic positions were relaxed until residual forces were lower than 0.01 eV/atom. The structures resulting from relaxation are displayed in Figure S90.

4.2. Calculations in toluene

Table S7 Ground state relative ΔG° and ΔE of studied molecules in kcal/mol, def2-TZVPP basis set was used. For structure abbreviations please see Figure S90.

Isomer/Molecule	ΔG° ω B97XD			ΔE CCSD(T)		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
Z	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
E	0.0	1.3	0.7	1.3	1.8	1.1
PT ₁	10.3	9.0	10.7	11.4	10.5	11.9
PT ₂	19.1	18.7	23.9	19.9	19.5	20.2
PT ₃	15.0	15.3	15.7	15.5	15.3	15.5
PT ₄	13.4	12.8	14.1	14.0	13.2	14.3

Table S8 Vertical excitation energies (nm) and oscillator strengths (in parentheses) for studied molecules in toluene calculated using TD-PBE0/def2-TZVPP method. First excited state is reported all cases. For molecule 2-E the S₁ has small oscillator strength, experimentally blueshifted S₂ is observed and also reported here.

Isomer/Molecule	1	2	3
Z	355 (0.55)	397 (0.50)	412 (0.30)
E	320 (0.85)	397 (0.07)/315 (0.76)	368 (0.31)/315 (0.56)
PT ₁	450 (0.51)	444 (0.52)	498 (0.32)
PT ₂	491 (0.29)	496 (0.27)	483 (0.21)
PT ₃	429 (0.43)	505 (0.13)	424 (0.40)
PT ₄	476 (0.46)	482 (0.26)	515 (0.31)

Table S9 Ground state activation ΔG^\ddagger and ΔE^\ddagger in kcal/mol. For structure abbreviations please see next Figure. Def2-TZVPP basis set was used.

Transformation	ΔG^\ddagger ω B97XD			ΔE^\ddagger CCSD(T)		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
E→Z	34.3	31.4	34.4	37.1	35.5	37.6
PT ₁ →Z	-1.3*	-1.5*	-1.9*	0.4	0.7	0.2
PT ₂ →PT ₁	8.6	5.6	4.9	7.9	5.8	8.7
PT ₄ →PT ₁	21.2	20.0	21.6	19.2	18.3	19.5

*Stable saddle point on the potential energy surface but unstable on Gibbs free energy surface

Figure S90 Isomers and transition states for their transformation in the molecule **3**.

4.3. Conical intersections

Figure S91 Minimal energy conical intersections localized in connection with relaxation of the (Z)-2 isomer excited state. Energies (MRSF BHHLYP/6-31G(d)) are relative to optimized excited structure of Z*, all values in kcal/mol.

Figure S92 Potential energy surface scan calculated using the TD- ω B97XD/def2-TZVPP approach in S₁ starting from the excited state minimum 3-Z* toward 3-PT₁ structure. The CNNC(fluorophenyl)

hydrazone skeleton was kept frozen to simulate effects of the crystal environment. Energy decrease for short distances relates to rotation of pyridine moiety towards conical intersection (MECI_{pyr} structure Figure S91).

4.4. Solid state modelling (finite-size model)

Table S10 Relative stability of tetramer structures. Please see Computational details for a description of partial optimization employed.

Tetramer composition	Relative energy ω B97XD/def2-SVP [kcal/mol]	
	2	3
4× Z	0.0	0.0
3× Z + 1× PT₂	22.2	24.1

Figure S93 Absorption spectrum of the tetramer structures: 4× Z (Z: black line) and 3× Z + 1× PT₂ (Mixture: red line). Vertical excitation energies (TD-PBE0/def2-SVP) and oscillator strengths broadened by gaussian functions (FWHM = 30 nm) were used.

4.5. Solid phase modelling (periodic model)

Figure S94 Relaxed structures of (Z)-**2** (top) and PT₂-**2** (bottom) along with the cell parameters obtained by PBC-DFT geometry optimizations. The transferred proton is encircled. Color coding: hydrogen (white), carbon (grey), nitrogen (blue), oxygen (red) and fluorine (green).

4.6.Raman spectra simulation

Mixture composition Z:PT ₂	Spectrum
95:5	
90:10	
70:30	

Figure S95 Overlaid simulated (ω B97XD/def2-SVP) Raman spectrum in the region 1100-1600 cm^{-1} of **3-Z** isomer (black), mixture of **3-PT₂** and **3-Z** (red). Different compositions of the mixture are compared to pure **3-Z**.

Mixture composition Z:PT ₂	Spectrum
95:5	
90:10	
70:30	

Figure S96 Overlaid full simulated (ω B97XD/def2-SVP) Raman spectrum of **3-Z** isomer (red), mixture of **3-PT₂** and **3-Z** (black). Different compositions of the mixture are compared to pure **3-Z**.

Figure S97 Basis set effects in Raman calculations: Top panel: Changes in Raman spectrum of triaryl HAZ **3** powder after 365 nm laser irradiation (Inset: color changes accompanying the sample irradiation recorded by optical microscopy; the estimated probing depth is 5 μm). Bottom panel: Left – displacement vectors for vibrations with highest activity in PT_2 structure; Right – comparison of theoretically predicted Raman spectrum for (Z)-**3** versus mixture (Z)-**3** and (PT₂)-**3**. The $\omega\text{B97XD/def2-TZVPP}$ level of theory in toluene (SMD model) was used and Raman shifts were scaled by an empirical factor 0.98. Please note that ν_1 and ν_2 are overlapping in this calculation resulting in one stronger peak of the mixture. For comparison see the main text Figure 11.

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